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450092, Ufa, st. S. Kuvykina, 18/1-47. Tel. : +7 (347) 262-82-35
Official site: <https://ip-journal.ru/>
E-mail: redactor.vestnic@gmail.com

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РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

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**ON AN ALGORITHM FOR SOLVING A BOUNDARY
VALUE PROBLEM FOR FREDHOLM
INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS**

E.A. Bakirova,

Kazakh National Women's Teacher Training University

Zh.M. Kadirbayeva,

International Information Technology University

S.S. Alimbekova,

Kazakh National Women's Teacher Training University,

Almaty

Annotation: This paper presents an algorithm to solve three-point boundary value problems for Fredholm integro-differential equations. Solving a problem for the Fredholm integro-differential equations is reduced to solving a system of linear algebraic equations. Numerical method for finding solution of the problem is suggested, which based on the solving the constructed system and Cauchy problem on the subintervals.

Keywords: boundary value problem, integro-differential equation, Dzhumabaev parametrization method, numerical algorithm

**ОБ АЛГОРИТМЕ РЕШЕНИЯ КРАЕВОЙ ЗАДАЧИ
ДЛЯ ИНТЕГРОДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНЫХ
УРАВНЕНИЙ ФРЕДГОЛЬМА**

Э.А. Бакирова,

Казахский национальный женский педагогический университет

Ж.М. Кадырбаева,

Международный университет информационных технологий

С.С. Алимбекова,

Казахский национальный женский педагогический университет,
Алматы

Аннотация: В статье представлен алгоритм решения трехточечной краевой задачи для интегро-дифференциальных уравнений Фредгольма. Решение задачи для интегро-дифференциальных уравнений Фредгольма сводится к решению системы линейных алгебраических уравнений. Предлагается численный метод решения задачи, основанный на решении построенной системы и задачи Коши на подынтервалах.

Ключевые слова: краевая задача, интегро-дифференциальное уравнение, метод параметризации Джумабаева, численный алгоритм

Consider the following linear three-point boundary value problem for Fredholm integro-differential equation

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = A(t)x + \int_0^T \varphi(t)\psi(s)x(s)ds + f(t), t \in (0, T), \quad (1)$$

$$B_0x(0) + B_1x(\theta) + B_2x(T) = d, d \in R^n, x \in R^n, \quad (2)$$

where the $(n \times n)$ – matrices $A(t)$, $\varphi(t)$, and $\psi(t)$ are continuous on $[0, T]$;

the n -vector $f(t)$ is continuous on $[0, T]$; B_0 , B_1 and B_2 are constant $(n \times n)$ - matrices, $0 < \theta < T$, and $\|x\| = \max_{i=1, n} |x_i|$.

Let $C([0, T], R^n)$ denote the space of continuous on $[0, T]$ functions $x(t)$ with norm $\|x\|_1 = \max_{t \in [0, T]} \|x(t)\|$.

Solution to problem (1), (2) is a continuously differentiable on $(0, T)$ function $x(t) \in C([0, T], R^n)$ satisfying the system of integro-differential equations (1) and boundary condition (2).

Mathematical modeling of many physical systems leads to integro-differential equations in various fields of engineering and physics. The role of integro-differential equations in the investigation of processes with after effects was noted in the monograph [1], and the overview of early works devoted to the initial and boundary value problems for integro-differential equations was provided as well. For the various aspects of qualitative theory and approximate methods for integro-differential equations, and their applications we refer to [1-12].

In this paper we use the Dzhumabaev parameterization method [13] to solve the linear three-point boundary value problem for Fredholm integro-differential equation (1), (2). This method is based on dividing the interval $[0, T]$ into N parts and introducing the additional parameters.

In this paper we have the points: $t_0 = 0 < t_1 = \theta < t_2 = T$, and let Δ_1 denote the partition of interval $[0, T)$ into 2 subintervals $[0, T) = [t_0, t_1) \cup [t_1, t_2)$.

Define the space $C([0, T], \Delta_1, R^{2n})$ of systems of functions $x[t] = (x_1(t), x_2(t))$, where $x_r: [t_{r-1}, t_r) \rightarrow R^n$ are continuous on $[t_{r-1}, t_r)$ and have finite left-sided limits $\lim_{t \rightarrow t_r-0} x_r(t)$ for all $r = 1, 2$, with norm $\|x[\cdot]\|_2 = \max_{r=1, N+1} \sup_{t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r)} \|x_r(t)\|$.

The restriction of the function $x(t)$ to the r -th interval $[t_{r-1}, t_r)$ is denoted by $x_r(t)$, i.e. $x_r(t) = x(t)$ for $t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r)$, $r = 1, 2$. Then we introduce additional parameters $\lambda_r = x_r(t_{r-1})$, $r = 1, 2$. Making the substitution $x_r(t) = z_r(t) + \lambda_r$ on every r -th interval $[t_{r-1}, t_r)$, $r = 1, 2$, we obtain the boundary value problem with parameters

$$\frac{dz_r}{dt} = A(t)[z_r + \lambda_r] + \sum_{j=1}^2 \int_{t_{j-1}}^{t_j} \varphi(t)\psi(s)[z_j + \lambda_j]ds + f(t),$$

$$t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r), r = 1, 2, \tag{3}$$

$$z_r(t_{r-1}) = 0, r = 1, 2, \tag{4}$$

$$B_0\lambda_1 + B_1\lambda_2 + B_2\lambda_2 + B_2 \lim_{t \rightarrow T-0} z_2(t) = d, \tag{5}$$

$$\lambda_1 + \lim_{t \rightarrow t_1-0} z_1(t) = \lambda_2. \tag{6}$$

A pair $(z^*[t], \lambda^*)$ with elements $z^*[t] = (z_1^*(t), z_2^*(t)) \in C([0, T], \Delta_1, R^{2n})$, $\lambda^* = (\lambda_1^*, \lambda_2^*) \in R^{2n}$ is said to be a solution to problem (3)-(6) if the functions $z_r^*(t)$, $r = 1, 2$, are continuously differentiable on $[t_{r-1}, t_r)$ and satisfy (3) and additional conditions (5), (6) with $\lambda_j = \lambda_j^*$, $j = 1, 2$, and initial conditions (4).

Problems (1), (2) and (3)-(6) are equivalent problems. For fixed λ_j problem (3), (4) is a special Cauchy problem for the system of Fredholm integro-differential equations.

Using the fundamental matrix $X_r(t)$ of differential equation $\frac{dx}{dt} = A(t)x$ on $[t_{r-1}, t_r]$, $r = 1, 2$, we reduce the special Cauchy problem for the system of integro-differential equations with parameters (3), (4) to the equivalent system of integral equations

$$z_r(t) = X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) A(\tau) d\tau \lambda_r + X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) f(\tau) d\tau + \\ + X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) \sum_{j=1}^2 \int_{t_{j-1}}^{t_j} \varphi(\tau) \psi(s) [z_j(s) + \lambda_j] ds d\tau, \\ t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r), r = 1, 2. \quad (7)$$

Let $\mu = \sum_{j=1}^2 \int_{t_{j-1}}^{t_j} \psi(s) z_j(s) ds$ and rewrite the system (7) in the following form

$$z_r(t) = X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) \varphi(\tau) d\tau \mu + X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) A(\tau) d\tau \lambda_r + \\ + X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) \varphi(\tau) \sum_{j=1}^2 \int_{t_{j-1}}^{t_j} \psi(s) \lambda_j ds d\tau + \\ + X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) f(\tau) d\tau, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r), r = 1, 2. \quad (8)$$

Multiplying both sides of (8) by $\psi(t)$, integrating on the interval $[t_{r-1}, t_r]$ and summing up over r , we get the system of linear algebraic equations with respect to μ :

$$\mu = G(\Delta_1) \mu + V_1(\Delta_1) \lambda_1 + V_2(\Delta_1) \lambda_2 + g(f, \Delta_1), \quad (9)$$

with the $(n \times n)$ matrices

$$G(\Delta_1) = \sum_{r=1}^2 \int_{t_{r-1}}^{t_r} \psi(\tau) X_r(\tau) \int_{t_{r-1}}^{\tau} X_r^{-1}(s) \varphi(s) ds d\tau, \\ V_r(\Delta_1) = \int_{t_{r-1}}^{t_r} \psi(\tau) X_r(\tau) \int_{t_{r-1}}^{\tau} X_r^{-1}(s) A(s) ds d\tau + \sum_{j=1}^2 \int_{t_{j-1}}^{t_j} \psi(\tau) \times \\ \times X_j(\tau) \int_{t_{j-1}}^{\tau} X_j^{-1}(\tau_1) \varphi(\tau_1) d\tau_1 d\tau \int_{t_{r-1}}^{t_r} \psi(s) ds, r = 1, 2,$$

and vectors of dimension n

$$g(f, \Delta_1) = \sum_{r=1}^2 \int_{t_{r-1}}^{t_r} \psi(\tau) X_r(\tau) \int_{t_{r-1}}^{\tau} X_r^{-1}(s) f(s) ds d\tau.$$

Then the system (9) has the form

$$[I - G(\Delta_1)] \mu = V_1(\Delta_1) \lambda_1 + V_2(\Delta_1) \lambda_2 + g(f, \Delta_1), \quad (10)$$

where I is the identity matrix of dimension n .

Let present $[I - G(\Delta_1)]^{-1}$ in the form $[I - G(\Delta_1)]^{-1} = M(\Delta_1)$, where $M(\Delta_1)$ are the square matrices of dimension n .

Then according to (10) the elements of vector $\mu \in R^n$ can be determined by the equalities

$$\mu = M(\Delta_1) V_1(\Delta_1) \lambda_1 + M(\Delta_1) V_2(\Delta_1) \lambda_2 + M(\Delta_1) g(f, \Delta_1). \quad (11)$$

In (8), substituting the right-hand side of (11) instead of μ , we get the representation of functions $z_r(t)$ via $\lambda_j, j = 1, 2$:

$$z_r(t) = X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) \varphi(\tau) d\tau \{M(\Delta_1) V_1(\Delta_1) \lambda_1 + M(\Delta_1) V_2(\Delta_1) \lambda_2\} + \\ + \sum_{j=1}^2 \left\{ X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) \varphi(\tau) d\tau \int_{t_{j-1}}^{t_j} \psi(s) ds \right\} \lambda_j + X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) A(\tau) d\tau \lambda_r +$$

$$+X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau)[\varphi(\tau)M(\Delta_1)g(f, \Delta_1) + f(\tau)]d\tau, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r], r = 1,2. \quad (12)$$

Introduce the notations:

$$D_{1,1}(\Delta_1) = X_1(t_1) \int_{t_0}^{t_1} X_1^{-1}(\tau)\varphi(\tau)d\tau \left[M(\Delta_1)V_1(\Delta_1) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \psi(s)ds \right] + X_1(t_1) \int_{t_0}^{t_1} X_1^{-1}(\tau)A(\tau)d\tau,$$

$$D_{1,2}(\Delta_1) = X_1(t_1) \int_{t_0}^{t_1} X_1^{-1}(\tau)\varphi(\tau)d\tau \left[M(\Delta_1)V_2(\Delta_1) + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \psi(s)ds \right],$$

$$D_{2,1}(\Delta_1) = X_2(t_2) \int_{t_1}^{t_2} X_2^{-1}(\tau)\varphi(\tau)d\tau \left[M(\Delta_1)V_1(\Delta_1) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \psi(s)ds \right],$$

$$D_{2,2}(\Delta_1) = X_2(t_2) \int_{t_1}^{t_2} X_2^{-1}(\tau)\varphi(\tau)d\tau \left[M(\Delta_1)V_2(\Delta_1) + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \psi(s)ds \right] + X_2(t_2) \int_{t_1}^{t_2} X_2^{-1}(\tau)A(\tau)d\tau,$$

$$F_1(\Delta_1) = X_1(t_1) \int_{t_0}^{t_1} X_1^{-1}(\tau)[\varphi(\tau)M(\Delta_1)g(f, \Delta_1) + f(\tau)]d\tau,$$

$$F_2(\Delta_1) = X_2(t_2) \int_{t_1}^{t_2} X_2^{-1}(\tau)[\varphi(\tau)M(\Delta_1)g(f, \Delta_1) + f(\tau)]d\tau.$$

Then from (12) we get

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow t_r-0} z_r(t) = D_{r,1}(\Delta_1)\lambda_1 + D_{r,2}(\Delta_1)\lambda_2 + F_r(\Delta_1). \quad (13)$$

Substituting the right-hand side of (13) into the conditions (5) and (6), we have the following system of linear algebraic equations with respect to parameters λ_1, λ_2 :

$$[B_0 + B_2D_{2,1}(\Delta_1)]\lambda_1 + [B_1 + B_2 + B_2D_{2,2}(\Delta_1)]\lambda_2 = d - B_2F_2(\Delta_1), \quad (14)$$

$$[I + D_{1,1}(\Delta_1)]\lambda_1 - [I - D_{1,2}(\Delta_1)]\lambda_2 = -F_1(\Delta_1). \quad (15)$$

Denoting by $Q_*(\Delta_1)$ the matrix corresponding to the left-hand side of the system of equations (14), (15), we get

$$Q_*(\Delta_1)\lambda = -F_*(\Delta_1), \lambda \in R^{2n}, \quad (16)$$

where $F_*(\Delta_1) = (-d + B_2F_2(\Delta_1), F_1(\Delta_1))$.

It is not difficult to establish that the solvability of the problem (6), (7) is equivalent to the solvability of the system (16). The solution of the system (16) is a vector λ^* : $\lambda_r^* = x^*(t_{r-1}), r = 1,2$.

Further we consider the Cauchy problems for ordinary differential equations on subintervals

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = A(t)y + P(t), y(t_{r-1}) = 0, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r], r = 1,2, \quad (17)$$

where $P(t)$ is either $(n \times n)$ matrix, or n vector, both continuous on $[t_{r-1}, t_r], r = 1,2$. Consequently, solution to problem (17) is a square matrix or a vector of dimension n . Denote by $a(P, t)$ the solution to the Cauchy problem (17). Obviously,

$$a(P, t) = X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau) P(\tau) d\tau, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r],$$

where $X_r(t)$ is a fundamental matrix of differential equation (17) on the r -th interval.

We offer the following numerical implementation of the Dzhumabaev parametrization method. The algorithm is based on the Bulirsch-Stoer method to solve the Cauchy problems for ODE and it is based on Simpson's method for estimation of the definite integrals.

1. Suppose we have a partition: $t_0 = 0 < t_1 = \theta < t_2 = T$. Divide each r -th interval $[t_{r-1}, t_r]$, $r = 1, 2$, into N_r parts with step $h_r = (t_r - t_{r-1})/N_r$. Assume on each interval $[t_{r-1}, t_r]$ the variable \hat{t} takes its discrete values: $\hat{t} = t_{r-1}$, $\hat{t} = t_{r-1} + h_r, \dots, \hat{t} = t_{r-1} + (N_r - 1)h_r, \hat{t} = t_r$, and denote by $\{t_{r-1}, t_r\}$ the set of such points.

2. Using the Bulirsch-Stoer method, we find the numerical solutions to Cauchy problems (17), where $P(t) = \varphi(t)$ and define the values of $(n \times n)$ matrices $a_r^{hr}(\varphi, \hat{t})$ on the set $\{t_{r-1}, t_r\}$, $r = 1, 2$.

3. Using the values of $(n \times n)$ matrices $\psi(s)$ and $a_r^{hr}(\varphi, \hat{t})$, on $\{t_{r-1}, t_r\}$ and Simpson's method, we calculate the $(n \times n)$ matrices

$$\hat{\psi}_r^{hr}(\varphi) = \int_{t_{r-1}}^{t_r} \psi(\tau) a_r^{hr}(\varphi, \tau) d\tau, r = 1, 2.$$

Summing up the matrices $\hat{\psi}_r^{hr}(\varphi)$ over r , we find the $(n \times n)$ matrices $G^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) = \sum_{r=1}^2 \hat{\psi}_r^{hr}(\varphi)$, where $\tilde{h} = (h_1, h_2) \in R^n$. Check the invertibility of matrix $[I - G^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1)]: R^n \rightarrow R^n$. If this matrix is invertible, we find $[I - G^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1)]^{-1} = M^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1)$. If it has no the inverse, then we take a new partition.

1. Solving the Cauchy problems for ordinary differential equations

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = A(t)y + A(t), y(t_{r-1}) = 0, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r],$$

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = A(t)y + f(t), y(t_{r-1}) = 0, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r], r = 1, 2,$$

by using again the Bulirsch-Stoer method, we find the values of $(n \times n)$ matrices $a_r(A, \hat{t})$, and n vector $a_r(f, \hat{t})$ on $\{t_{r-1}, t_r\}$, $r = 1, 2$.

2. Applying Simpson's method on the set $\{t_{r-1}, t_r\}$, we evaluate the definite integrals

$$\hat{\psi}_r^{hr} = \int_{t_{r-1}}^{t_r} \psi(s) ds, \hat{\psi}_r^{hr}(A) = \int_{t_{r-1}}^{t_r} \psi(\tau) a_r^{hr}(A, \tau) d\tau,$$

$$\hat{\psi}_r^{hr}(f) = \int_{t_{r-1}}^{t_r} \psi(\tau) a_r^{hr}(f, \tau) d\tau, r = 1, 2.$$

By the equalities

$$V_r^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) = \hat{\psi}_r^{h_r}(A) + \sum_{j=1}^2 \hat{\psi}_j^{h_j}(\varphi) \cdot \hat{\psi}_r^{h_r}, r = 1,2, g^{\tilde{h}}(f, \Delta_1) = \sum_{r=1}^2 \hat{\psi}_r^{h_r}(f),$$

we define the $(n \times n)$ matrices $V_r^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1), r = 1,2,$ and n vectors $g^{\tilde{h}}(f, \Delta_1).$

3. Construct the system of linear algebraic equations with respect to parameters

$$Q_*^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1)\lambda = -F_*^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1), \lambda \in R^{2n}, \tag{18}$$

The elements of matrix $Q_*^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1)$ and vector

$$F_*^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) = \left(-d + CF_2^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1), F_1^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1)\right)$$
 are defined by the equalities

$$D_{r,i}^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) = a_r^{h_r}(\varphi, t_r) \left[M^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) V_i^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) + \hat{\psi}_i^{h_i} \right], i \neq r, r, i = 1,2,$$

$$D_{r,r}^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) = a_r^{h_r}(\varphi, t_r) \left[M^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) V_r^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) + \hat{\psi}_r^{h_r} \right] + a_r^{h_r}(A, t_r),$$

$$F_r^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) = a_r^{h_r}(\varphi, t_r) M^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) g^{\tilde{h}}(f, \Delta_1) + a_r^{h_r}(f, t_r), r = 1,2.$$

Solving the system (18), we find $\lambda^{\tilde{h}}$. As noted above, the elements of $\lambda^{\tilde{h}}=(\lambda_1^{\tilde{h}}, \lambda_2^{\tilde{h}})$ are the values of approximate solution to problem (1), (2) in the starting points of subintervals: $x^{\tilde{h}_r}(t_{r-1}) = \lambda_r^{\tilde{h}}, r = 1,2.$

4. To define the values of approximate solution at the remaining points of set $\{t_{r-1}, t_r\},$ we first find

$$\mu^{\tilde{h}} = M^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) V_1^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) \lambda_1 + M^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) V_2^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) \lambda_2 + M^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_1) g^{\tilde{h}}(f, \Delta_1),$$

and then solve the Cauchy problems

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = A(t)x + \mathcal{F}^{\tilde{h}}(t), x(t_{r-1}) = \lambda_r^{\tilde{h}}, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r], r = 1,2, \tag{19}$$

where $\mathcal{F}^{\tilde{h}}(t) = \varphi(t) \left[\mu^{\tilde{h}} + \sum_{j=1}^2 \hat{\psi}_j^{h_j} \lambda_j^{\tilde{h}} \right] + f(t).$

And the solutions to Cauchy problems (19) are found by the Bulirsch-Stoer method. Thus, this algorithm allows us to find the numerical solution to the three-point boundary value problem for Fredholm integro-differential equation (1), (2).

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